

Gas Volumetric Estimation of SOOH in Organic Sulphinic Acids.

BY S. KRISHNA AND BHAGWAN DAS.

The characteristic property of the carboxyl group in organic acids is that it liberates iodine from a mixture of pure potassium iodide and iodate, and the reaction proceeds more or less quantitatively accordingly to the equation.—

The iodine can be quickly and accurately determined by measuring the volume of oxygen which it liberates on treating it with a freshly prepared alkaline solution of hydrogen peroxide :

As in most cases the liberation of iodine by the action of organic acids on alkali iodide and iodate is slower than the mineral acids, so Kux (*Zeit. anal. Chem.*, 1893, 32, 129) investigated the different conditions under which the common organic acids (R.COOH) could be estimated quantitatively by gas volumetric iodine process. The reaction usually proceeds at ordinary temperatures, but in certain cases the reaction is rather slow, but is appreciably accelerated by the action of heat.

The method has also been employed successfully in case of certain derivatives of the acids that contain positive groups. But it fails when such negative groups as sulphonic, sulphinic, nitro or hydroxyl are present. The reason obviously being that these also liberate iodine from the mixture of potassium iodide and iodate, and in certain cases, it has been noticed that the liberated iodine reacts very quickly with the compound replacing the original group altogether. Experiments in this direction have been carried out by Datta and Bhoumic (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 303) who have found that when a current of chlorine gas is introduced into an aqueous solution of sulphinic acid, the sulphinic group

is detached with the simultaneous production of the corresponding chloro-derivatives.

where X represents the organic radicle to which the sulphonic group is attached.

It has also been found that aromatic bodies which already contain an hydroxy group, as in the case of phenols and oxy-acids, exhibit a special facility in the displacement of sulphonic group by chlorine: thus anisole and phenetole sulphonic acids have given tetrachloro-ketodihydrobenzene.

Pope and Wood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1827) found that a mixture of alkali bromide and bromate acts better in the replacement of sulphonic groups, though in some cases it causes an oxidising effect especially if there are easily oxidisable groups, *para* or *ortho* to each other; for example, aniline sulphonic acid gives chloro-quinone.

From the above discussion it was concluded that the action of potassium iodide and iodate on aromatic sulphonic acids was not always in accordance with the Kux's equation, but instead it effected the replacement of sulphonic group and at the same time produced a compound containing iodine in the benzene nucleus. Similar results have been obtained by Krishna and Pope on the action of KI and KI₃ on some hydroxy acids (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 798). From their experiments on salicylic acid, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, 3:5-nitro-salicylic acid and 3:5-dinitro-salicylic acid, it was found that the amount of iodine liberated fell much below the quantity demanded by Kux's iodine equation. It has been found that in each case the COOH group is completely removed from the nucleus and its place is taken up by iodine that is produced during the reaction, the corresponding tri-iodophe-

nol being produced in each case. This brings the reaction into agreement with the well known case of the replacement of acidic groups in aromatic sulphonic acids. Therefore under these circumstances, it is not possible to determine the carboxyl group by the usual Kux's method.

The present work has been conducted to study similar reactions with organic sulphinic acids. It has been found that when an aqueous solution of potassium iodide and iodate in certain proportions is added to an aqueous solution of benzene sulphinic acid, there is an evolution of free iodine, shown by the colour produced, which has been found to be in agreement with the equation,

The reaction has been investigated in the case of the following sulphinic acids, which were prepared according to the well-known methods.

Acids.	M. p.	References.
Benzene sulphinic acid	85°	Gattermann, <i>Ber.</i> , 1899, 32, 1141.
<i>p</i> -Tolyl sulphinic acid.	86-87°	Do.
<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene sulphinic acid.	160-82°	Stewart, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1922, 121, 2557.
<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene- <i>o</i> -sulphinic acid.	139°	Krishna, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1928, 123, 157.
<i>m</i> -Sulphinobenzoic acid.	197-96°	Gattermann, <i>loc. cit.</i>
<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene sulphinic acid.	140°	Do.
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzene sulphinic acid.	93-94°	Do.
<i>p</i> -Methoxy tolylsulphinic acid.	97-96°	Do. p. 1143.
<i>p</i> -Sulphino-acetanilide.	160°	Stewart, <i>loc. cit.</i>
<i>o</i> -Sulphino-salicylic acid.	159°	Do.
<i>m</i> -Benzene disulphinic acid.	118-19°	Autenreith, <i>Ber.</i> , 1903, 36, 189.
<i>p</i> -Sulphino-cinnamic acid.	140-42°	Stewart, <i>loc. cit.</i> , p. 2560.
<i>p</i> -Bromobenzene sulphinic acid.	117°	Do.
<i>p</i> -Anisol sulphinic acid.	98°	Smiles, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1922, 121, 2558.

Acids.	M. p.	References.
<i>p</i> -Phenetol sulphinic acid ...	104—106°	Gattermann, <i>loc. cit.</i> p. 1144.
<i>p</i> -Nitro-toluene sulphinic acid ...	...	
Naphthalene sulphinic acid ...	104—105°	Gattermann, <i>loc. cit.</i>
<i>p</i> -Sulphino phenyl acetic acid ...	142°	Smiles, <i>loc. cit.</i>
Guaiacol sulphinic acid.	...	

In all the cases studied there is no detachment of the sulphinic group from the molecule, as has been observed in the case of sulphonic group, nor is there any evidence of the production of iodo derivatives. Therefore Kux's gas volumetric method can be applied for the quantitative estimation of sulphinic group. The reaction proceeds normally at the room temperature (15—20°C), undue rise of temperature having a detrimental effect due to the loss of iodine.

The general factors essential to the success of the experiment are the purity of the reagents, and an approximate adjustment of the proportions in which these are mixed. Potassium iodide and iodate used must be acid free. It is found advisable not to use more than double the theoretical quantity of hydrogen peroxide and about six times the theoretical amount of potash. A freshly made solution of one part of potassium hydroxide free from carbonates, in one part of distilled water (free from carbon dioxide) and 2 to 3 % solution of hydrogen peroxide were found to yield the best results.

The method of procedure in the beginning was conducted on the lines of Kux's iodine method. It was found that on adding a warm (50—80°) solution of the acids in small portions at a time to a warm aqueous solution of potassium iodide and iodate (in proportions demanded by the equation given above) and digesting the mixture on the water-bath for some time (usually twenty minutes) the amount of iodine liberated fell much below the quantity demanded by the equation and involved an error of more than 25% in many cases. Heating or longer digestion were therefore found to be inadmissible, and instead an ice cold aqueous acid solution added to an ice cold mixture of potassium iodide and

iodate, and this brought to the room temperature (18-20°) was found to yield the best results.

An attempt has been made to explain the mechanism of the reaction. Very probably, the first step in the reaction is the formation of a sulphonyl iodide :

which reacts further with the alkaline hydrogen peroxide and liberates the requisite amount of oxygen.

That sulphonic iodide is the first product of reaction is shown by the fact that on addition of potassium iodide and potassium iodate solution to sulphinic acid a thick yellow precipitate always results as has been isolated in many cases and found to be sulphonic iodides. Instances of the formation of sulphonic iodides have been found by Hinsberg (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 2896). The iodides have been found to be rather unstable bodies which break up into free iodine and the acid, thereby attaining an equilibrium. The free iodine liberated can be estimated by the usual method with standard thiosulphate solution, but only in such cases where the liberation of iodine is complete and there is no formation of intermediate sulphonic iodides, but where the iodide has not completely decomposed into iodine and acid, and the liberation of iodine is not quantitative, it is not possible to estimate the free iodine with thiosulphate solution.

In some cases in the solutions a white precipitate is observed and this probably is a disulphone. Instances of the formation of these disulphones have been found by Hinsberg (*loc. cit.*) where he has investigated that organic sulphides are converted into sulphoxides and disulphoxides (R. SO₂S. R) which absorb oxygen and get converted into disulphones. A reference may also be made to the work of Hilditch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, II, 1524) in this connection. In the present case the formation of disulphones may be represented according to the equation :

Another evidence of the formation of disulphones may be gathered from the following facts. In all the cases studied, it was noticed

that the volume of oxygen in the Lunge nitrometer had to be recorded just a couple of minutes after the completion of the reaction as further delay involved an absorption of about 2 c. c. of oxygen in an hour's duration. This fact may therefore be explained on the conversion of sulphinic acid to sulphoxides and disulphones.

From the above discussion it is clear that Kux's gas volumetric method for the estimation of carboxyl group in organic acids, can, with slight experimental modifications, be successfully applied in the determination of -SOOH group in sulphinic acids, which have in the nucleus such groups as -NO₂, -Cl, -Br, -OH, -CH₃, -OCH₃, -COOH, -CH:CH.COOH, CH₂.COOH, -NH.CO.CH₃, -OC₂H₅.

In all such cases where another sulphinic group or a carboxyl group is present in the molecule, the oxygen liberated is double the usual volume, since both the groups now take part in the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphinic acids were prepared by the usual methods from the corresponding sulphonyl chlorides. As the literature on the subject does not give complete details for obtaining sulphinic acids in good yields, it is thought desirable to give an account of a typical reduction of the sulphonyl chlorides to the corresponding sulphinic acids.

A mixture of 20 gms. of the sulphonyl chloride and 50 gms. of sodium sulphite (Na₂SO₃. 9H₂O) and 100 gms. of crushed ice was shaken for three hours, until the sulphonyl chloride had dissolved. The mixture was tested for alkalinity from time to time and dilute sodium hydroxide was added to prevent formation of sulphur dioxide. The mixture was kept cold by further addition of ice, any undue increase of temperature being fatal to the success of the experiment on account of hydrolysis of the sulphonyl chloride. The mixture was filtered, and acidified slowly with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid, when sulphinic acids (usually crystalline) separated. The yield of sulphinic acid is in almost all cases about 80-90 per cent. Recrystallised acids were thoroughly dried by keeping them in vacuum desiccator before using. These gave the usual test with phenetole and sulphinic acid (Smiles' test).

About 0.2 gm. of well powdered sulphinic acid which had been thoroughly dried by keeping in a vacuum desiccator for two days was dissolved in 40 c.c. of hot water and cooled in ice. To this was added in small portions at a time an ice cold mixture of potassium iodide (2 g.) and potassium iodate (0.2 g.). The mixture was brought to the room temperature and washed into an outer vessel *A* of the apparatus

shown. Into the inner vessel *B* was put a freshly made and cooled mixture of 2 c.c. of 3 per cent. hydrogen peroxide solution, and 4 c.c. of caustic potash, 1:1. The stopper was inserted and the Lunge nitrometer was filled with water. The level in the two tubes was adjusted by closing the stop cock *D*, and turning the stop cock *E* in such a position that the connection was made with the outside atmosphere and the nitrometer; and the level in the nitrometer tube is raised zero by raising the level in the levelling tube *F*. *E* was then turned so that the connection was between the outside atmosphere and the reaction vessel *A*. *D* was then opened and allowed to remain in that position for about five minutes so that *A* should come to the atmospheric pressure. *E* was then turned so that the connection was made between the nitrometer and the reaction vessel. The vessel *A* was given a rotatory motion and gradually tipped on one side to mix the contents of the vessel *B* with contents of the vessel *A*. Gentle shaking is continued till the level of water remains constant. Oxygen evolved was collected at a low pressure. The reaction is

complete in half a minute and after a minute's cooling the level of the tube was adjusted again and the volume of oxygen collected was noted, and the amount of SOOH calculated in terms of oxygen. Several such readings were taken and the mean results are tabulated below.

Gas Volumetric Estimation of SOOH in Organic Sulphinic Acids.

Sulphinic Acid.	Amount of acid (in gm.)	Vol. of O ₂ liberated at N. T. P. (in c.c.).	% SOOH found (in gms.).	% SO ₂ H cal. (in gms.).	Error.
Benzene sulphinic Acid ...	0.249	19.56	45.58	45.77	-.19
p-Toluene sulphinic acid ...	0.232	16.70	41.78	41.87	+ .11
p-Chloro-benzene sulphinic acid ...	0.294	18.68	36.78	36.88	-.05
p-Dichloro-benzene sulphinic acid ...	0.252	13.86	30.77	30.80	-.03
p-Bromobenzene sulphinic acid ...	0.333	16.86	29.89	29.41	-.02
p-Dibromo-benzene sulphinic acid ...	0.284	10.58	21.82	21.87	-.05
6 :3-Chloro-nitro-benzene sulphinic acid.	0.310	15.67	29.84	29.84	.00
p-Nitro-toluene sulphinic acid ...	0.295	16.42	32.29	32.39	-.04
p-Anisole sulphinic acid ...	0.324	21.06	37.72	37.79	-.07
p-Phenetole sulphinic acid ...	0.321	19.35	34.98	34.94	+ .04
Sulphino-acetanilide ...	0.281	15.89	32.83	32.66	+ .17
p-Sulphino-phenyl acetic acid ...	0.232	31.86	32.27	32.50	-.23
4-Sulphino-cinnamic acid ...	0.269	28.36	30.59	30.66	-.07
Sulphino-benzoic acid ...	0.231	27.78	34.80	34.94	-.04
p-Sulphino-salicylic acid ...	0.241	26.74	32.21	32.18	+ .03
p-Methoxy tolyl sulphinic acid ...	0.265	15.95	34.93	34.94	-.01
Guaicol sulphinic acid ...	0.275	16.39	34.59	34.57	+ .02
Naphthalene sulphinic acid ...	0.306	17.70	33.57	33.86	-.29
m-Benzene disulphinic acid ...	0.263	29.32	63.52	63.10	+ .42